

Evaluation of Antioxidants and Antibacterial Activities of *Lactuca Serriola* (L.) Leaves Extracts against Bacteria Isolated from Diabetic Foot Ulcers

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Received: Mar 13, 2026

Accepted: Apr 13, 2026

Published: Apr 19, 2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Natural products remain crucial as a foundation for drug discovery. *Lactuca serriola* (L), a member of the family Astereceae, is one of such plants used in traditional medicine.

Objective: The present research aims to evaluate the biological activity of *L. virosa* leaf extract as antioxidant and antibacterial agent,

Methods: Different concentrations of ethanol (Solvent A (100%), Solvent B (75%), Solvent C (50%), and Solvent D (25%)) and distilled water (Solvent E) were used for extraction of *Lactuca serriola* (L.) leaf parts by maceration method. Extracts at concentrations of 100, 75, 50, and 25 mg/ml were prepared for each solvent to detect antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using agar well diffusion method. The antioxidant activity was assessed using the DPPH assay.

Results: Solvent A achieved the highest antioxidant activity, while Solvent D recorded the lowest effect. All concentrations of extracts inhibited bacterial growth, and the inhibition effect increased with increasing extract concentration. The highest inhibition zone against *S. aureus* was recorded at Solvent D with 100 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD = 26.00 \pm 2.65 mm), while the highest inhibition zone against *P. aeruginosa* was recorded at Solvent I with 100 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD = 26.00 \pm 2.65 mm).

Conclusion: the possibility of using ethanolic extracts as antibacterial and antioxidant agent

Keywords: *Lactuca serriola* (L.), Ethanol extraction, Antimicrobial activity, Antioxidant activity

1. INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have been used as a form of treatment for thousands of years, making them one of the oldest sources of medicine. Their therapeutic benefits have been passed down through generations within various human communities across the globe [1]. Natural products remain crucial as a foundation for drug discovery, and today, many modern pharmaceuticals are derived from traditional herbal remedies. Research into naturally derived medications integrates the disciplines of chemistry, pharmacology, and botany. The isolation, identification, and quantification of constituent compounds within plant materials constitute core aspects of their chemical characterization [2]. Extensive research has demonstrated that numerous plant species exhibit pharmacological activities, primarily attributed to their secondary metabolites [3]. The medicinal value of natural products is due to the presence of chemical compounds that exert specific pharmacological effects on the human body; flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds [4].

L. serriola commonly known as wild lettuce or bitter lettuce is one of the traditional medicinal plants belonging to the Asteraceae family contains numerous phytochemical constituents, including phytosterols, essential oils, lignin's, saponins, phenolic acids, and sterols, which exhibit significant medicinal effects [5]. has long been recognized in folk medicine for its antioxidant, antimicrobial, antifungal analgesic, sedative, and anti-inflammatory properties. Despite the effectiveness of biological plant extracts, they may exhibit cytotoxic effects that depend on both cell type and concentration. This necessitates evaluating cytotoxicity to ensure the safety of their therapeutic use, especially in topical applications involving direct contact with living tissue [7]. Furthermore, the rapid emergence of pathogenic bacteria resistant to conventional drugs has rendered the search for bioactive compounds from natural sources essential for the development of new curative agents [8]. Therefore, the current study aimed to evaluate the biological activities of *L. virosa* leaf extracts through: (1) extraction of active chemical compounds from dried leaves using different solvents; (2) evaluation of antioxidant activity using the DPPH radical scavenging assay (3) evaluation of antimicrobial activity *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. (3) Testing the inhibitory ability of the extracts from the plant *L. serriola* and against bacteria associated with diabetic foot infections.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Plant Collection

The dried leaves of *L. serriola* were obtained from gardens in Najaf City in October 2025. The plant material was cleaned, ground using an electric grinder, collected in plastic bags, and stored at room temperature until use.

2.2. Bacterial Isolates

This study was conducted at the Faculty of Science, University of Kufa, from October 2025 to March 2026. Pure isolates of *S. aureus* (as a Gram positive) and *P. aeruginosa* (as a Gram negative) were obtained from Al-Ameen Center for Research and Advanced Biotechnology, Najaf, Iraq. Both isolates were associated with diabetic foot ulcer (DFU).

3. Testing Methods

3.1. Preparation of plant extracts

Ten grams of dried powdered leaves of each plant were extracted separately by maceration using 200 ml of 5 different concentration ethanol as a solvent as followed: solvent A consist of 100% ethanol, solvent B consist of 75% ethanol + 25% distilled water , solvent C consist of 50% ethanol + 50% distilled water, solvent D consist of 25% ethanol + 75% distilled water, and solvent E consist of 100% distilled water. Each mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for 24 hours at room temperature, filtered through cloth and Winlab No.1 filter paper, then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. The filtrate was dried at 40°C for 24 hours and stored at 4°C until use.

3.2. Preparation of extract concentrations

Four concentrations were prepared from each extract by dissolving 0.1, 0.15, 0.20, and 0.30 g of dry powder to yield final concentrations of 100, 150, 200, and 300 mg/mL, respectively. Aqueous extracts were dissolved directly in distilled water, while ethanolic extracts were first dissolved in DMSO then in ethanol [9].

3.3. Antioxidant test by DPPH free radical scavenging assay

The free radical scavenging activity of the extracts was evaluated [10]. Sample solutions at concentrations of 1, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.12 mg/mL were each mixed with 0.3% DPPH methanol solution and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes in the dark. Absorbance was

measured at 517 nm and ascorbic acid (AA) was used as a positive control. The percentage of DPPH inhibition was calculated as follows:

$\text{Inhibition\%} = (\text{Absorbance of control} - \text{Absorbance of test sample}) / \text{Absorbance of control} \times 100$. The IC_{50} value was determined from the curve of inhibition percentage plotted against concentration.

3.4. Identification of bacterial isolates

Bacterial identification of all bacterial isolates was based on colony morphology, Gram staining, hemolysis on blood agar, and biochemical tests including oxidase, catalase, coagulase, urease, MacConkey agar, and mannitol salt agar [11].

3.5. Antibacterial activity

Agar well diffusion method [10] has been followed up for detection antibacterial activity. Briefly, all bacterial isolates were activated by incubation in Brain Heart infusion agar for 24 hr. at 37°C under aerobic conditions, then the culture media were diluted until gave OD equal to MacFarland tube NO. 0.5, then 100 µl of bacterial suspension was cultured Muller Hinton Agar (MHA) by spreading method. Five well on cultured MHA were done and filled with 100µl of each concentration of solvents then incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. Antibacterial activity was detected by measuring the diameter of inhibition zone around each well.

4. Results

4.1. Antioxidant activity of solvent E extracts of *L. serriola*

Table 1 demonstrated the antioxidant activity of solvent E extractes of *L. serriola* leaves in vitro. The highest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with (E) solvent extract at concentration of 1mg/ml which recorded 87.420 ± 0.995 A_{Ba}; while the lowest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with 0.12 mg/ml D.W extract which recorded about 72.593 ± 1.099 A_{Bd}. Also, the results showed that concentration of 0.5 mg/ml and 0.25 mg/ml recorded 85.698 ± 3.052 A_{Bb} and 80.208 ± 1.000 A_{Bc} respectively with a significant differences with other concentrations. The results show that the solvent extract with 1 mg/ml exhibited good antioxidant activity and significantly difference with other concentrations.

4.2. Antioxidant activity of solvent A extract of *L. serriola*

The results (Table1) showed that the highest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with solvent A extract at concentration of 1mg/ml which recorded 87.878 ± 1.054 A_a and significantly difference with control group (P) solvent and with all concentrations studies, while the lowest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with 0.12 mg/ml D.W extract which recorded 75.861 ± 0.954 A_d and significantly difference with control group (P) solvent and with all concentrations study. Also, the results revealed that concentration of 0.5 mg/ml and 0.25 mg/ml recorded 87.246 ± 1.010 A_b and 80.973 ± 1.005 A_c respectively and significantly differences with other concentrations.

4.3. Antioxidant activity of solvent B of *L. serriola*

However, the results also showed that the highest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with solvent B extract at concentration of 1mg/ml which recorded 89.165 ± 1.001 C_a and significantly difference with control group and other concentrations, while the lowest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with 0.12 mg/ml D.W. extract which recorded 66.552 ± 1.901 C_d.

4.4. Antioxidant activity of solvent C of *L. serriola*.

Results in table 1 demonstrated the antioxidant activity of solvent C extracts of *L. serriola*. The highest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with solvent C extract at concentration of 1mg/ml which recorded 86.627 ± 2.052 B_a, while the lowest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with 0.12 mg/ml D.W extract which recorded

74.186 ± 2.642 **Bd**. Data also showed that concentration of 0.5 mg/ml and 0.25 mg/ml which recorded 81.862 ± 0.954 **Bb** and 79.673 ± 2.052 **Bc** respectively and significant differences with other concentrations.

4.5. Antioxidant activity of solvent D of *L. serriola*

Also, the results demonstrated the highest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with solvent D extract at concentration of 1mg/ml which recorded 76.765 ± 2.722 **Ea**, while the lowest antioxidant activity was found in the mixture of DPPH with 0.12 mg/ml D.W extract which recorded 55.940 ± 3.999 **Ed**. Data showed that concentration of 0.5 mg/ml and 0.25 mg/ml which recorded 72.460 ± 2.645 **Eb** and 71.891 ± 3.100 **Ec** respectively and significant differences with other concentrations.

Table (1) Antioxidant activity of different solvents of ethanolic and D.W extracts of *L. serriola* leaves

Extract\ Conc. (mg/ml)	Solvent Abbreviation	Mean ±SD of Antioxidant Activity of <i>L. serriola</i> leaves extract at concentration:				
		0.12 mg/ml	0.25 mg/ml	0.5 mg/ml	1 mg/ml	Total
Ascorbic acid 100%	P	69.089 ± 1.000 Dd	69.402 ± 2.001 Dc	69.544 ± 1.020 Db	77.072 ± 1.010 Da	71.28 ± 3.68
Distilled Water 100%	E	72.593 ± 1.099 ABd	80.208 ± 1.000 ABc	85.698 ± 3.052 ABb	87.420 ± 0.995 ABa	81.48 ± 6.22
Ethanol 100%	A	75.861 ± 0.954 Ad	80.973 ± 1.005 Ac	87.246 ± 1.010 Ab	87.878 ± 1.054 Aa	82.99 ± 5.21
Ethanol 75%	B	66.552 ± 1.901 Cd	68.215 ± 1.003 Cc	84.059 ± 3.464 Cb	89.165 ± 1.001 Ca	77.00 ± 10.39
Ethanol 50%	C	74.186 ± 2.642 Bd	79.673 ± 2.052 Bc	81.862 ± 0.954 Bb	86.627 ± 2.052 Ba	80.59 ± 4.98
Ethanol 25%	D	55.940 ± 3.999 Ed	71.891 ± 3.100 Ec	72.460 ± 2.645 Eb	76.765 ± 2.722 Ea	69.26 ± 8.70
Total		69.04 ± 7.07	75.06 ± 5.72	80.14 ± 7.18	84.15 ± 5.49	77.10 ± 8.48
LSD, p-value		LSD Solvent = 1.655 P<0.001*				
		LSD Concentration = 1.3515 P<0.001*				

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (Mean ± SD). Different capital letters within the same column indicate significant differences among solvents, while different small letters within the same row indicate significant differences among concentrations according to the LSD test. Differences were considered statistically significant at P < 0.001.

4.5. Antibacterial activity of Solvent E of *L. serriola* against *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas*

Results shown in the figure 1 and table 2 for Solvent **E** extract of *L. serriola* against *S. aureus* revealed a significant difference in inhibition zone among all concentrations (100 , 75, 50 and 25 mg/ml) compared with the control group of ethanolic extracts (Solvent **A**). Also, Solvent **E** extract at concentration 100 mg/ml showed significant differences with all concentrations and compared with the control group (Mean ±SD=22.00±1.00 **bC**) and recorded the highest inhibition zone compared with other concentration and control group

solvent A which recorded 20.00 ± 1.00 bC). The lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml average was 0.08 ± 0.03 aC) compared to other concentrations (75 and 50 mg/ml respectively). A significant difference in inhibition zone with all studied concentrations was recorded to D.W extract at concentration 75 mg/ml where Mean \pm SD= 20.00 ± 2.00 bC). Concentration 50 mg/ml recorded the inhibition zone at Mean \pm SD= was 15.00 ± 1.73 aC) compared with other studied concentrations.

Data in the table 3 for Solvent E extract from of *L. serriola* against *Pseudomonas* showed significant differences in inhibition zone among all concentrations (100 , 75, 50 and 25) mg/ml compared with the control group ethanolic extracts Solvent A as shown in figure 2.

The Solvent E extract at concentration 100 mg/ml revealed significant differences with all concentrations and compared with the control group (Mean \pm SD= 19.00 ± 1.00 bB), and recorded the highest inhibition zone compared with other concentration. The lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml where Mean \pm SD= was 10.00 ± 1.73 bB) compared to other concentrations (50 and 75 mg/ml respectively) as shown in figure 2. Also, significant differences in inhibition zone with all concentrations of D.W extract at concentration 75 mg/ml was shown (Mean \pm SD= 14.00 ± 2.00 bB). At Concentration 50 mg/ml Mean \pm SD of inhibition zone at was 11.00 ± 1.00 aB compared with other concentrations studies.

Figure 1: Antibacterial activity of Distilled Water solvent E extracts of *L. serriola* leaves against: A: *Pseudomonas auregenosa*, B: *Staphylococcus aureus*

Extract \ Conc.	Mean \pm SD of inhibition zone at concentration				Total
	300 mg/ml	200 mg/ml	150 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	
Distilled Water 100%	22.00 ± 1.00 bC	20.00 ± 2.00 bC	15.00 ± 1.73 aC	0.08 ± 0.03 aC	14.27 ± 9.04 C
Ethanol 100%	20.00 ± 1.00 bC	18.00 ± 2.00 bC	14.00 ± 2.65 aC	0.13 ± 0.06 aC	13.03 ± 8.23 C
Ethanol 75%	22.00 ± 2.00 bB	18.00 ± 1.73 bB	15.00 ± 2.00 aB	11.00 ± 1.00 bB	16.50 ± 4.46 B
Ethanol 50%	15.00 ± 1.00 aD	13.00 ± 0.00 aD	11.00 ± 1.00 aD	0.08 ± 0.03 aD	9.77 ± 6.06 D
Ethanol	26.00 ± 2.65	22.00 ± 2.00	15.00 ± 1.00	9.00 ± 1.00	18.00 ± 6.98

25%	cA	cA	aA	bA	A
Total	21.00±3.96 B	18.20±3.43 C	14.00±2.20 D	4.06±5.09 E	14.32±7.47
LSD, p-value	LSD Extract= 1.264 P < 0.001*				
	LSD Conc. = 2.765 P < 0.001*				

4.6. Antibacterial activity of ethanolic Solvent A of *L. serriolla* against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*

The results of present study (Table 2, Figure 2) revealed significant differences in inhibition zone toward *S. aureus* among all concentrations compared with the control group. At concentration 100 mg/ml, there were significant differences with all concentrations and compared with the control group (Mean \pm SD= 20.00 \pm 1.00 bC), while the lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD= 0.13 \pm 0.06 aC) compared to other concentrations 50 and 75 mg/ml respectively.

Also, Data in the table 3 and figure 2 show presence of significant differences in inhibition zone of solvent A against *P. aeruginosa* among all concentrations (100, 75, 50 and 25 mg/ml) compared with the control group (Mean \pm SD= 16.00 \pm 2.65 aC, Mean \pm SD= 0.33 \pm 0.06 aC, Mean \pm SD= 14.00 \pm 1.00 bC, and Mean \pm SD= 11.00 \pm 1.73 aC respectively).

Figure 2: Antibacterial activity of ethanolic solvent A extract of *L. serriolla* against: **A:** *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* **B:** *Staphylococcus aureus*

4.7. Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extract Solvent B of *L. serriolla* against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*

The highest Mean \pm SD in inhibition zone of the ethanolic extract Solvent B against *S. aureus* was 22.00 \pm 2.00 bB compared with other concentrations studies respectively, while the lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD= 11.00 \pm 1.00 bB) compared to other concentrations 75 and 50 mg/ml recorded about (18.00 \pm 1.73 bB) and (15.00 \pm 2.00 aB) respectively. (Table 2, Figure 3).

Also, Data in the table 3 reported that the ethanolic extract (Solvent C) shows presence of significant differences in inhibition zone of *P. auregenosa* among all concentrations (100,75,50 and 25 mg/ml) compared with the control group.

Figure 3: Antibacterial activity of ethanolic solvent B extract of *L. serriolla* against: **A:** *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* **B:** *Staphylococcus aureus*

4.8. Antibacterial activity of ethanolic extract Solvent C of *L. serriolla* against *S. aureus* and *P. auregenosa*

Table 2 showed the significant differences in the inhibition zone among all concentration (100,75,50 and 25 mg/ml) of ethanolic extract Solvent C (50%) against *S. aureus* compared with the control group. In the 100 mg/ml ethanolic extract the highest inhibition zone was reported where Mean \pm SD was 15.00 ± 1.00 aD compared with other concentrations studies respectively. The lowest inhibition zone recorded at 75 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD was 13.00 ± 0.00 aD) compared to other concentrations 50 and 25 mg/ml respectively (Figure 4). At concentration 50 mg/ml of solvent C, Mean \pm SD of inhibition zone was 11.00 ± 1.00 aD compared to the control group (Figure 4).

Table (3) showed that Solvent C of ethanolic extract (50%) against *P. auregenosa* shows significant differences in inhibition zone among all concentrations (100,75,50 and 25 mg/ml) compared with the control group. In the 100 mg/ml ethanolic extract at show in the same table , recorded the highest inhibition zone at average was (19.00 ± 1.73 bB) compared with other concentrations studies respectively.

The lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml (0.33 ± 0.15 aB) compared to other concentrations 75 and 50 mg/ml respectively (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Antibacterial activity of ethanolic solvent C extracts of *L. serriolla* against:
A: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* B: *Staphylococcus aureus*

4.9. Antibacterial activity of ethanolic solvent D extract of *L. serriolla* against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*

Data in the Table2 show that the ethanolic extract solvent D has significant differences in inhibition zone against *S.aureus* among all concentrations (100,75,50 and 25)mg/ml compared with the control group. At 100 mg/ml ethanolic extract showed the highest inhibition zone (Mean \pm SD= 26.00 ± 2.65 cA) compared with other studied concentrations. The lowest Mean \pm SD in inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml (9.00 ± 1.00 bA) compared to other concentrations 75 and 50 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD= 22.00 ± 2.00 cA, and 15.00 ± 1.00 aA respectively) as shown in table 2 and figure 5.

Also, Table 3 showed that the ethanolic extract solvent D has significant differences in inhibition zone against *P. auregenosa* among all concentrations (100,75,50 and 25mg/ml) compared with the control group. At 100 mg/ml ethanolic extract showed the highest inhibition zone (Mean \pm SD= 26.00 ± 2.65 cA) compared with other studied concentrations. The lowest inhibition zone recorded at 25 mg/ml (Mean \pm SD= 9.00 ± 1.00 bA) compared to other concentrations 75 and 50 mg/ml where it was 22.00 ± 2.00 cA, and 15.00 ± 1.00 bA respectively.

Figure 5: Antibacterial activity of ethanolic solvent D extracts of *L. serriolla* against:
 A: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* B: *Staphylococcus aureus*

Table 3: Antibacterial activity of <i>L. serriolla</i> ethanolic extracts against <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>					
Extract \ Conc.	Mean \pm SD of inhibition zone at concentration:				Total
	300 mg/ml	200 mg/ml	150 mg/ml	100 mg/ml	
Distilled Water 100%	19.00 \pm 1.00 bB	14.00 \pm 2.00 bB	11.00 \pm 1.00 aB	10.00 \pm 1.73 bB	13.50 \pm 3.87 B
Ethanol 100%	16.00 \pm 2.65 aC	14.00 \pm 1.00 bC	11.00 \pm 1.73 aC	0.33 \pm 0.06 aC	10.33 \pm 6.47 C
Ethanol 75%	14.00 \pm 2.00 aD	12.00 \pm 0.00 aD	10.00 \pm 1.73 aD	0.27 \pm 0.06 aD	9.07 \pm 5.62 D
Ethanol 50%	19.00 \pm 1.73 bB	14.00 \pm 1.00 bB	12.00 \pm 1.73 aB	0.33 \pm 0.15 aB	11.33 \pm 7.24 B
Ethanol 25%	26.00 \pm 2.65 cA	22.00 \pm 2.00 cA	15.00 \pm 1.00 bA	9.00 \pm 1.00 bA	18.00 \pm 6.98 A
Total	18.80\pm4.57 B	15.20\pm3.80 C	11.80\pm2.18 D	3.99\pm4.73 E	12.45\pm6.73
LSD, p-value	LSD Extract= 1.265 P < 0.001*				
	LSD Conc. = 1.132 P < 0.001*				

5. Discussion

5.1. Antioxidant Activity

Data in this results showed that ,the absolute ethanol extract exhibited high efficacy in DPPH radical scavenging that increased proportionally with concentration, attributable to the capacity of pure ethanol to extract flavonoid compounds such as quercetin and luteolin, which possess multiple hydroxyl groups enabling them to efficiently transfer hydrogen atoms to the free radical and convert it to its stable form. [12] demonstrated in *L. serriola* leaves that alcoholic extracts contain elevated concentrations of luteolin, quercetin, and rutin, and that these flavonoids are responsible for the antioxidant activity measured by the DPPH method via the hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) mechanism. The ethanolic Solvent (A) of *L. serriola* recorded the higher antioxidant activity than aqueous Solvent (E) extract among all extracts investigated, despite the presence of hydrophilic compounds with antioxidant potential such as tannins and polar phenolic acids. The 75% ethanol extract solvent (B) exhibited the highest

antioxidant activity among all extracts, attributable to the solvent polarity balance between ethanol and water, which renders the solvent more efficient in extracting the phenolic and flavonoid compounds responsible for DPPH radical scavenging. In contrast, the 25% ethanol extract solvent (D) recorded the lowest activity among the alcoholic extracts, confirming that a low ethanol concentration is insufficient to disrupt hydrogen bonds or dissolve semipolar flavonoid compounds. This was corroborated by [13], who demonstrated that the extraction efficiency of phenolic and flavonoid compounds responsible for free radical scavenging decreases significantly when ethanol concentrations below 50% are employed, with the 70% ethanol extract recording the highest total phenolic content and the best DPPH antioxidant activity compared to concentrations of 30% and 50%.

The variation in antioxidant activity among *L. serriola* extracts reflects the influence of solvent polarity on the selectivity of extraction of phenolic and flavonoid compounds responsible for DPPH scavenging. [14] confirmed the presence of chlorogenic acid, quercetin, and coumaric acid in *L. serriola* extracts compounds well known for their free radical scavenging capacity via the electron transfer (SET) and hydrogen atom transfer (HAT) mechanisms as their aromatic hydroxyl groups donate hydrogen atoms to the DPPH• radical, converting it to its stable form (DPPH-H).

5.2. Antibacterial Activity

Results of this study were compatible with Rashad [15] as mentioned that the aqueous extract of *S. aureus* was an effective antibacterial agent because of the extract activity in penetrating the bacterial cell wall. [16] concluded from their study that ethanolic extracts of *S. aromaticum* have antibacterial and anticarcinogenic activities against *S. mutans*. This study is compatible with my study which proved that antibacterial activity increases with increasing concentration for all extract types.

These results compatible with the findings of many researchers, including [17] reported that Gram-positive bacteria were more sensitive to active Phytochemicals in ethanolic extract than the Gram-negative bacteria, this may be because that the Gram-positive bacteria have cell wall-less complex than gram-negative bacteria and lack sieve effects against large molecules because of the small pores in their cell envelope. Data in this results, agreement with study by [18] investigation that the extract of Prickly lettuce leaves with difference solvent system was more effective for *S. aureus* than and *P. aeruginosa* because the chemical structural composition of the bacteria cell wall, as Gram positive lacks a layer of outer membranes, which makes the permeability of substances which effected the cell greater compared to Gram negative bacteria which have its inner wall is an internal barrier represented by lipopolysaccharide combined with multiple proteins which can prevent the passage of many harmful substances into the cell [18] was concluded that antibacterial effects of the ethanolic extracts against *S. aureus* depend on their concentration. These extracts destroy the membrane and cell wall, which leads to the loss of vital intracellular substances and result in bacterial cell death. From results show in the same table and the same figures the bacteria *P. aeruginosa* more effected by all concentration of leaves *L. virosa* extracts than *S. aureus* bacteria because bacteria possess various strategies have been suggested to overcome the resistance of antibiotics and their phytochemicals. [19]. One strategy related to cell wall layers and biofilm formation. Research of [20] reported that there are multiple targets for the antibacterial agents that comprise (i) bacterial protein bio synthesis; (II) bacterial cell-wall biosynthesis; (iii) bacterial cell membrane destruction; (iv) bacterial DNA replication and repair, and (v) inhibition of a metabolic pathway.

Research by [21] reported that, *L. serriola* Aqueous leaves extracts showed that, significant differences inhibition growth zones of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at ($P \leq 0.05$) were 12, 8, 9, and 6 mm, respectively. This study showed there is a great potential of using *L. serriola* extracts as natural antimicrobials

for controlling pathogenic bacteria due to phytochemicals present in plant study. These results, compatible with the findings of many researchers including [22] concluded the possibility of using ethanolic extracts against *S. aureus* which were resistant to beta-lactamase antibiotics, and when bacteria isolate mixing these extracts, showed synergistic action that prevented the development of bacterial resistance. Studying by [23] founds that *L. serriola* plant is a medicinal plant that has been possesses various pharmacological activities because rich in many phytochemicals as follows: sesquiterpenes, monoterpenes, hydrocarbon, and phenolic compounds. Eugenyl acetate, eugenol, are the most significant phytochemicals in *L. serriola* against pathogenic bacteria. [24] mentioned that both aqueous and ethanolic extracts have an inhibitory effect against *S. aureus* and that the ethanolic extract showed higher antibacterial activity, the reason may be that ethanol is organic and thus has a strong interaction with the bacterial cell. Statistical analysis shows that the results showed that all solvent system concentrations of plant extracts gave bacterial inhibition zone and increased with increased of plant extract concentration.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Kufa University, evaluated and approved the research protocol (H K/1063, dated October 2025).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interests

FUNDING

The author(s) disclaim any receipt of financial assistance for the research, writing, and/or publishing of this paper.

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